

YIELD RESPONSE OF MUSTARD AS INFLUENCED BY WEED MANAGEMENT PRACTICE UNDER CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE SYSTEM

M. M. Hossain^{1*}, M. Begum¹, A. Hashem², M. M. Rahman¹, R. W. Bell³ and M. E. Haque³

ABSTRACT

Conservation agriculture practice based on increased residue retention are being developed in Bangladesh but the optimum weed control for crops in the cropping sequence is still not defined. The present experiment aimed to determine the effectiveness of increased residue retention relative to pre- and post-emergence herbicide treatment on weed control and yield of mustard planted after rice. An on-farm experiment was conducted at Durbachara village, Mymensingh district during post rice season (October 2014 to January 2015). Mustard *cv. BARI sharisha-14*, was sown with six tillage and weed control practices *viz.*, Conventional tillage + farmer's weeding practice (Control); Roundup (RU) + Strip tillage (ST); RU + ST + Pre-emergence (PE) herbicide (Pendimethalin); RU + ST + Post-emergence (PO) herbicide (Oxadiazon); RU+ ST + PE + PO; RU+ ST + weed-free (WF), and two levels of rice residue *viz.*, **R₂₀**: 20% residue and **R₅₀**: 50% residue. Conventional tillage produced higher weed density and biomass compared to strip tillage. WF retained 50% residue yielded the highest (1.72 tha⁻¹) which was 67% higher compared to control retained 20% residue (1.03 tha⁻¹). Although WF retained 50% residue yielded the highest, the highest BCR (4.39) was calculated from RU+ ST + PE + PO retained 50% residue which was 7% higher compared to WF with 50% residue.

Keywords: Mustard, yield, weed management, herbicide, strip tillage, conservation agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

Conservation agriculture (CA) system, which is characterized by minimum soil disturbance with residue management (Mukherjee and Debnath, 2013) and in recent years the spread of CA has gathered even more momentum as a new paradigm for 'sustainable production intensification' (Kassam, 2014). Widespread resource degradation problems under conventional system, and the need of reducing production costs, increasing profitability and making agriculture more competitive, have made the CA system more imperative. Globally innovations of CA based crop management technologies are said to be more efficient, use less inputs, improve production and income, and address the emerging problems (Gupta and Seth, 2007). Presently, about 125 M ha area is practiced following the concepts and technologies for CA (Friedrich *et al.*, 2012); the major countries being USA, Brazil, Argentina, Canada and Australia (FAO, 2012).

Weed species shifts and losses in crop yield as a result of increased weed density have been cited as major hurdles to the widespread adoption of CA. Crop yield losses in CA due to weeds may vary depending on weed dynamics and weed intensity. However, the recent development of broad-spectrum herbicides provides an opportunity to control weeds in CA and repeated use of these herbicides, leading to increased selection pressure for herbicide resistance (Lemerle and Hashem, 2014). But options for weed control must reduce selection pressure for herbicide resistance for providing a season-long weed suppression (Hossain *et al.*, 2014). In CA systems the presence of residue on the soil surface may influence soil temperature and moisture regimes that affect weed seed germination and emergence patterns over the growing season thus help in reducing weed infestation through reduced weed emergence (Sharma *et al.*, 2013) and influence crop yield. Crop yields can be similar for conventional and conservation tillage systems if weeds are controlled

¹Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh-2202, ²Department of Agriculture and Food, Western Australia, ³Murdoch University, Australia
*Email: mmhshakil@yahoo.com

and crop stands are uniform (Mahajan *et al.*, 2002). Considering the above facts, an on-farm experiment was conducted, to examine the performance of tillage practices and residue levels on crop and weeds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment on-farm was conducted at the Durbacakra village at the Vangnamari Union under Gouripur Upazila of Mymensingh district of Bangladesh from 24 October 2014 to 11 January 2015. Mustard, CV. *BARI sharisha-14*, was sown with 6 tillage and weed control practices *viz.*, **T₁**: Conventional tillage + farmer's weeding practice (Control); **T₂**: Roundup (RU) + Strip tillage (ST); **T₃**: RU+ ST + Pre-emergence (PE) herbicide (Pendimethalin); **T₄**: RU+ ST + Post-emergence (PO) herbicide (Oxadiazon); **T₅**: RU+ ST + PE + PO; **T₆**: RU+ ST + weed-free, and 2 levels of crop residue *viz.*, **R₂₀**: Lower (20%) residue and **R₅₀**: Higher (50%) residue. The treatments were laid out in randomized complete block design with 4 replications using unit plots of 9 m × 5 m. Conventional tillage was done with two wheeler power tiller (2WPT) and strip tillage with versatile multi crop planter (VMP) machine. Pre-emergence herbicide was sprayed day after sowing (DAS) and the post-emergence at 20 DAS. Three hand weeding was done to keep the plots weed free. Weed densities were recorded randomly from 4 locations of 0.25 m² at 40 DAS. Weed dry matter assessed by harvesting biomass which was then oven dried at 70°C for 72 hours. The crop was harvested at maturity and data recorded. Data were subjected to ANOVA using MSTAT-C and means separated by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Effect of tillage and weed control practice on weed density and biomass

Control treatment produced the highest weeds (78 plants m⁻²) and biomass (56 gm⁻²) while RU+ST+PE+PO produced the lowest (37 plants per m⁻² and 7 gm⁻²) and both were nil in WF (table 1). Compared to RU+ST, RU+ST+PE reduced density by 12% and biomass by 40% while RU+ST+PO reduced density and biomass by 24% and 66%, respectively. RU+ST+PE+PO reduced density by 51% and biomass by 80% compared to RU+ST.

Table 1: Effect of tillage and weed control practice on weed density and biomass

Tillage and weed control practice	Weed density (no. m ⁻²)	Weed biomass (gm ⁻²)
CT	78a	56a
RU+ST	76a	35b
RU+ST+PE	69b	21c
RU+ST+PO	58c	12d
RU+ST+PE+PO	37d	7e
RU+ST+WF	0e	0f
LS	**	**
LSD _{0.05}	3.47	4.61
CV (%)	5.37	13.18

Effect of residue on weed density and biomass

The higher density (56 plants m⁻²) and biomass (24 gm⁻²) was recorded from 50% residue compared to 20% residue (Table 2). Increased residue level (50%) reduced the weed density by 23% and biomass by 33% compared to 20% residue.

Table 2: Effect of residue on weed density and biomass

Residue level	Weed density (no. m ⁻²)	Weed biomass (gm ⁻²)
R ₂₀	56a	24a
R ₅₀	43b	16b
LS	**	**
LSD _{0.05}	1.77	2.70
CV (%)	5.37	13.18

Interaction effect of tillage and weed control practice and residue level on weed density and biomass

Conventional practice retained 20% residue produced the highest density (83 plants m⁻²) and dry matter (68 gm⁻²) compared to 50% residue retained with RU+ST+PE+PO (32 plants m⁻² and 4 gm⁻², respectively) (Table 3). The highest weeds and biomass produced by the conventional practice interacted with 20% residue was similar to strip tilled roundup alone with same level of residue. It is clear from the results that, all the treatments with 50% residue produced the lower weeds and biomass compared to 20% residue.

Table 3: Interaction effect of tillage and weed control practice and residue level on weed density and biomass

Tillage and Weed control practice	Residue level	Weed density (no. m ⁻²)	Weed biomass (gm ⁻²)
CT	R ₂₀	83a	68a
	R ₅₀	74b	45b
RU+ST	R ₂₀	80a	39b
	R ₅₀	72b	32c
RU+ST+PE	R ₂₀	70bc	24d
	R ₅₀	66d	19e
RU+ST+PO	R ₂₀	59e	15ef
	R ₅₀	55f	9fg
RU+ST+PE+PO	R ₂₀	43g	8gh
	R ₅₀	32h	4h
RU+ST+WF	R ₂₀	0i	0i
	R ₅₀	0i	0i
LS		**	**
LSD _{0.05}		5.43	6.80
CV (%)		5.37	13.18

Effects of tillage and weed control practice on yield attributes and yield of mustard

Tillage and weed control practice exerted significant effect on number of pods per plant, seed yield, harvest index and BCR while rest of other attributes were non-significant (Table 4).

Weed free treatment produced the highest pods which was similar to strip tillage sprayed both pre-emergence and post-emergence herbicide. Strip tillage with pre-emergence herbicide and with post-emergence herbicide produced the similar number of pods plant⁻¹. The lowest number of pods was produced from the conventional practice which was similar to

strip tillage with roundup alone. The highest seed was yielded from the strip tilled weed free treatment which was 34% higher compared to conventional practice. Strip tillage sprayed both pre-emergence and post-emergence herbicides yielded 24% higher seed compared to control and ranked the second. Strip tillage with pre-emergence herbicide and with post-emergence herbicide yielded the similar yield. The lowest yield was recorded from the conventional practice that similar to strip tillage with roundup alone. It is clear from the data that, the higher the biomass the lower seed yield. The highest harvest index calculated from strip tilled weed free treatment while the lowest was from the conventional practice. Strip tillage with or without pre-emergence or post-emergence or both of two produced the similar harvest index. Although, strip tilled weed free treatment yielded the highest seeds, the highest BCR was calculated from strip tillage sprayed both pre-emergence and post-emergence herbicides, which was 37% higher compared to control and 12% higher compared to weed free. The lowest BCR was calculated from the conventional practice which was similar to strip tillage with roundup alone. Strip tillage with pre-emergence or post-emergence herbicide produced the similar BCR.

Table 4: Effects of tillage and weed control practice on yield attributes and yield of mustard

Tillage and weed control practice	Plants m ⁻²	Plant height (cm)	No. of branch plant ⁻¹	No of pods plant ⁻¹	Pod length (cm)	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield (tha ⁻¹)	Percent increase over control	Stover yield (tha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)	BCR	Percent increase over control
CT	64.33	119.00	8.95	93.47d	5.83	3.32	1.11c	---	1.54	41.89d	2.72d	---
RU+ST	65.47	117.58	9.87	96.41cd	5.78	3.35	1.17c	5.12	1.52	43.49bc	2.87d	5.22
RU+ST+PE	63.84	119.13	10.25	104.87c	5.96	3.40	1.26bc	12.04	1.52	45.32b	3.00c	9.33
RU+ST+PO	64.87	119.04	10.39	106.73c	5.87	3.45	1.29bc	13.95	1.53	45.74b	3.05c	12.41
RU+ST+PE+PO	64.56	118.75	12.75	124.31b	5.84	3.85	1.46b	24.26	1.65	46.95b	4.32a	37.04
RU+ST+WF	63.89	119.67	13.45	138.12a	6.11	3.83	1.69a	34.31	1.74	49.27a	3.85b	29.35
LS	NS	NS	NS	**	NS	NS	**		NS	**	**	
LSD _{0.05}	2.07	6.08	4.95	22.23	0.34	0.10	0.23		0.37	0.59	0.58	
CV (%)	6.37	5.06	41.83	16.24	5.77	3.16	1.55		2.09	1.67	1.74	

Effects of residue level on yield attributes and yield of mustard

Residue level exerted significant effect on number of pods per plant, seed yield and BCR and rest of all attributes were non-significant (Table 5). Increase residue (50%) produced 25% higher pods per plant which attributed to yield 14% higher seeds compared to lower (20%) residue level. Consequently 12% higher BCR was calculated from the 50% residue.

Table 5: Effects of residue on yield attributes and yield of mustard

Residue level	Plants m ⁻²	Plant height (cm)	No. of branch plant ⁻¹	No. of pods plant ⁻¹	Pod length (cm)	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield (tha ⁻¹)	Percent increase over control	Stover yield (tha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)	BCR	Percent increase over control
R ₂₀	65.84	119.54	10.12	102.37b	5.87	3.37	1.33b	--	1.72	44.61	3.06b	---
R ₅₀	66.43	118.18	13.45	127.51a	5.92	3.43	1.54a	13.63	1.84	45.56	3.49a	12.32
LS	NS	NS	NS	**	NS	NS	**		NS	NS	**	
LSD _{0.05}	3.87	3.51	2.86	12.83	0.19	0.63	0.13		1.21	0.37	0.33	
CV (%)	6.37	5.06	14.83	16.24	5.77	3.16	1.55		2.09	1.67	1.74	

Interaction effects of tillage and weed control practice on yield attributes and yield of mustard

Interaction among the treatments exerted significant effect on pod number, seed yield, harvest index and BCR. Rests of all other characters were non-significant (Table 6). The highest pods were recorded from the strip tilled weed free treatment interacted with 50% residue. Strip tilled weed free treatment retained with 20% residue produced the second highest pods which was similar to strip tilled sprayed with post-emergence herbicide only and strip tilled with pre-emergence herbicide followed by post-emergence herbicide treatment retained with 50% residue. Conventional practice retained with 20% residue produced the lowest pods similar to strip tillage with or without pre-emergence herbicide interacted with 20% residue. Conventional tillage with 50% residue produced the pods similar to strip tillage with or without pre-emergence herbicide retained with 50% residue and strip tillage with post-emergence or both of pre-emergence and post-emergence herbicide retained with 20% residue. The highest seed yield was recorded from weed free treatment with 20 or 50% residue.

Pre-emergence herbicide followed by post-emergence herbicide retained with 50% residue yielded the second highest seeds. Conventional tillage with 20 % residue yielded the lowest which is similar to strip tillage with roundup alone interacted with 20% residue. Strip tillage with pre-emergence or post-emergence herbicide retained with 50% residue yielded the similar seeds which are close to the yield produced by strip tillage sprayed with pre-emergence followed by post-emergence herbicide retained with 20% residue. Strip tillage sprayed with pre-emergence or post-emergence interacted 20% residue yielded similar seeds which was similar to conventional tillage with 50% residue.

Table 6: Interaction effects of tillage and weed control practice on yield attributes and yield of mustard

Tillage and weed control practice	Residue level	No. of Plants m ⁻²	Plant height (cm)	No. of branch plant ⁻¹	No. of pods plant ⁻¹	Pod length (cm)	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield (tha ⁻¹)	Stover yield (tha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)	BCR
CT	R ₂₀	63.78	120.08	8.11	76d	5.77	3.30	1.03g	1.42	42.04e	2.36i
	R ₅₀	64.55	117.92	10.21	109c	5.88	3.35	1.19e	1.64	42.05e	2.71g
RU+ST	R ₂₀	63.52	114.08	8.23	86d	5.76	3.35	1.07g	1.39	43.50d	2.62h
	R ₅₀	63.78	121.08	12.38	106c	5.80	3.35	1.28d	1.65	43.69d	3.31f
RU+ST+PE	R ₂₀	64.82	119.25	11.74	96d	5.95	3.37	1.15ef	1.38	45.45bc	2.74g
	R ₅₀	64.89	119.00	11.89	112c	5.97	3.42	1.37c	1.65	45.36bc	3.26e
RU+ST+PO	R ₂₀	64.53	121.83	12.34	112c	5.94	3.40	1.18e	1.41	45.56bc	2.80g
	R ₅₀	64.82	116.25	14.47	137b	5.80	3.50	1.40c	1.63	46.20b	3.32e
RU+ST+PE+PO	R ₂₀	64.49	121.17	12.12	117c	5.79	3.45	1.40c	1.58	46.98b	4.26b
	R ₅₀	65.74	116.33	14.43	140b	5.88	3.45	1.53b	1.72	47.08ab	4.39a
RU+ST+WF	R ₂₀	65.83	120.83	14.86	129b	6.02	3.35	1.66a	1.69	49.55a	3.60d
	R ₅₀	65.93	118.50	17.12	161a	6.19	3.50	1.72a	1.75	49.57a	4.12c
LS		NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	**	NS	**	**
LSD _{0.05}		10.12	8.60	7.00	10.96	0.48	0.15	0.32	0.47	0.48	2.89
CV (%)		6.37	5.06	41.83	16.24	5.77	3.16	1.55	2.09	1.76	1.67

Strip tilled weed free plots retained with 20 or 50% residue attributed the highest harvest index. Strip tillage with pre-emergence or post-emergence or combination of both herbicide retained with 20 or 50% residue produced the similar harvest index. Conventional tillage with 20 or 50% residue scored the lowest followed by strip tillage with roundup alone retained 20 or 50% residue. The highest BCR was calculated from strip tillage sprayed with pre-emergence followed by post-emergence herbicide retained with 50% residue while Conventional tillage interacted with 20% residue scored the lowest BCR. It was observed from the result that, all the treatments interacted with 50% residue produced the higher BCR compared to 20% residue.

CONCLUSION

Under conservation agriculture system, application of pre-emergence herbicide followed by a post-emergence herbicide retained higher level of residue managed the weeds successfully which attributed the maximum benefit of mustard.

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REFERENCES

- FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations). 2012. Available online at <http://www.fao.org/ag/ca/6c.html>.
- Friedrich, T., Derpsch, R., Kassam, A. H. 2012. Overview of the global spread of Conservation Agriculture. *Facts Reports, Special Issue 6*: 1-7.
- Gupta, R. K. and Seth, A. 2007. A review of resource conserving technologies for sustainable management of the rice-wheat cropping systems of the Indo-Gangetic Plains (IGP). *Crop Prot.*26: 436-447.
- Hossain, M. M., Begum, M., Rahman, M. M. and Hashem, M. A. 2014. Weed Management in Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under Minimum tillage and Crop Residues. *Proc. Conference on Conservation Agriculture for Smallholders in Asia and Africa*. 7-11 December 2014, Mymensingh, Bangladesh. Pp 33-35.
- Kassam, A. 2014. Overview of the current status of Conservation Agriculture globally and challenges with designing and adapting CA to the circumstances of the smallholders. *Proc. of the Conference on Conservation Agriculture for Smallholders in Asia and Africa*. 7-11, December 2014, Mymensingh, Bangladesh. Pp. 2-4
- Lemerle, D. and Hashem, A. 2014. Weed Management in Conservation Agriculture. *Proc. Conference on Conservation Agriculture for Smallholders in Asia and Africa*. 7-11 December 2014, Mymensingh, Bangladesh. Pp.101-103
- Mahajan, G., Brar, L. S. and Walia, U. S. 2002. *Phalaris minor* response in wheat in relation to planting dates, tillage and herbicides. *Indian J. Weed Sci.* 34: 213-215.
- Mukherjee, P. K. and Debnath, P. 2013. Weed control practices in maize (*Zea mays* L.) under conventional and conservation tillage practices. *Proc. 24th Asian-Pacific Weed Science Society Conference, October 22-25, 2013, Bandung, Indonesia*. Pp. 302-307.
- Sharma, A. R., Singh, V. P. and Raghwendra Singh. 2013. Weed management in conservation agriculture systems-problems and prospects. *Proc. 24th Asian-Pacific Weed Science Society Conference, October 22-25, 2013, Bandung, Indonesia*. Pp. 31-42.